

Research Paper

Nickel Sulphide Thin Film as a Potential Optical Amplifier for Phototherapy: An Analysis Using the Chemical Bath Deposition Method

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to determine the optical properties of Nickel Sulphide thin film, that is, reflectance, absorbance, transmittance and energy band gap from the method of chemical bath deposition (CBD) against several wavelengths and correlate with the various ultraviolet (UV) ranges for phototherapy treatments to determine its potential as an optical amplifier. The nickel sulphide thin film was chemically deposited by using nickel sulphate, sodium thiosulfate and triethanolamine (TEA) solutions. Based on the avantes single beam scanning UV-spectrophotometer, the optical property of NiS thin film, which is, the spectral absorbance, reflectance and transmittance were obtained. It was found that NiS thin film have high transparency in the desired wavelength UV ranges for phototherapy applications, a low absorption coefficient to minimize energy loss and maximize gain, a low reflection useful for minimizing reflection losses and maximize light coupling efficiency and an energy band gap of 1.98 eV making it a suitable semiconductor material. NiS thin film from this study is shown to possess the desired characteristics property of an optical amplifier for phototherapy.

Keywords: Phototherapy, Nickel Sulphide thin film, Chemical bath deposition, optical amplifier

Introduction

Phototherapy is a safe and effective treatment option for various skin conditions and disorders. It has been shown to be effective in the treatment of psoriasis, atopic dermatitis, vitiligo, acne vulgaris and hyperbilirubinemia [1-4]. In phototherapy applications, materials like photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) or photodiodes are often used for their sensitivity to UV light, as they can convert UV photons into electrical signals. For amplification of UV light for phototherapy, other techniques and materials like optical amplifiers (e.g., fiber amplifiers) or UV-sensitive photocells may be more suitable options to consider.

Thin films can be used to amplify UV radiation for

phototherapy. Thin films of certain materials, such as titanium dioxide or zinc oxide, can act as optical amplifiers by absorbing UV radiation and re-emitting it at a higher intensity. This amplification effect can be utilized in phototherapy treatments, where controlled exposure to UV radiation is used to treat certain skin conditions. The thin films can enhance the therapeutic effects of UV radiation by concentrating and increasing its intensity, potentially leading to more effective and efficient treatments.

Nickel sulfide (NiS) thin films have gained significant attention in recent years due to their interesting optical properties. Several studies have reported that NiS thin films show optical absorption in the visible and near-infrared regions. The deposition of NiS thin films on a glass substrate using chemical bath deposition (CBD)

method was reported to show that the films exhibited excellent transparency in the visible region and high absorption in the near-infrared range, a low reflectivity of the films in the visible region, indicating their potential use as anti-reflection coatings and enhanced nonlinear optical (NLO) properties in NiS thin films deposited on a quartz substrate [5-7].

Chemical bath deposition (CBD) is a method for depositing thin films onto a substrate using chemical reactions in a solution. CBD can be used to deposit films with various optical properties, such as high transparency and low refractive index [8-9]. In general, CBD offers a simple and cost-effective method for deposition of films with desirable optical properties. By controlling the reaction conditions and solution composition, it is possible to obtain films with specific optical properties suitable for various applications as phototherapy.

Nickel sulphide thin films are not commonly known to be used as optical amplifiers for phototherapy. Nickel sulphide thin films exhibit a wide range of optical properties, but their use as an optical amplifier for UV radiation in phototherapy is not well-documented. Illumination from phototherapy lamps reduces in intensity with prolonged continuous usage and the need for local materials as optical amplifiers necessitates this study. The study poses great significance in harnessing the optical properties of local materials as Nickel sulphide thin film, as optical amplifier in the design of phototherapy lamps for sustained intensity, usage and phototherapy dose optimization. The aim of the study is to determine the optical properties (reflectance, absorbance and transmittance) from the method of CBD using Nickel Sulphide thin film against several wavelengths and correlate with the various UV range for phototherapy treatments to determine its potential as an optical amplifier.

Materials and Methods

Solvents and reagents used for the thin film growth include: Nickel sulphate (NiSO_4), Triethanolamine ($(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3\text{N}$), Sodium Acetate, Distilled water, Thiourea. Microscopic Glass with size of slide $25.4 \times 76.2 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$ thick was used as the substrate.

Order of reaction in the chemical bath deposition

The method used in this study is the chemical bath deposition technique based on the precipitation and deposition of the desired compound. In order to avoid spontaneous precipitation of the reaction bath, a suitable complexing agent is added to the reaction bath to control the release of the metallic ion in the solution. The basic principle is that in order to precipitate a

certain compound from a solution, its ionic product (IP) must exceed the solubility product (SP). The total amount of all the solution in the chemical bath is 100ml. They include; 1.50g solution of NiSO_4 , 3g of Sodium Acetate, 15ml solution of TEA (triethanolamine) as a complexing agent. Its function is to trap the ions and release them gently on the substrate, it slow down the rate of deposition on the substrate but does not take part in the reaction. Increase in NH_3 reduces the acidity of the solution. Distilled water is the solvent (it makes the solution not to stick permanently on the chemical bath).

Preparation process

The substrates were first washed and rinsed with distilled water and detergent to remove any sticking dirt. The distilled water was used to rinse all the other apparatus used for chemical bath deposition of NiS_2 thin film. Beaker used was 100ml.

- NiSO_4 solution was prepared by dissolving 1.50g of NiSO_4 in 50ml of distilled water.
- Thiourea solution was obtained by dissolving of 7.6g of thiourea in 10ml of distilled water
- Sodium Acetate solution was obtained by dissolving 3g of sodium in 20ml of distilled water.

Table I. Solutions and their quantities

Solutions	Quantity (ml) of distilled water
NiSO_4	50
Tetraethanolamine (TEA)	15
Sodium Acetate	20
Thiourea	10
Distilled Water	5
Total	100

Four washed beakers of 100ml each was used for the preparation. The chemical bath deposition was prepared by putting 50ml of NiSO_4 solution with the aid of a syringe into the 100ml beaker each. 20ml of Sodium acetate solution was added gradually into the beaker. 15ml of TEA was then added and finally 10ml of thiourea was also added with continuous stirring to start the reaction, 5ml of distilled water was added to make up to the mark of the 100ml mark of the beaker. This mixture was done in the entire four beakers sequentially. Microscopic glass slide was used as the substrate. The substrate was then washed and rinsed with distilled water, dried in air. Cleaning of substrate surface is one of the first important steps in the film deposition procedure [10, 11]. The substrate was then inserted vertically into the solution bath for deposition with the aid of synthetic

foam. The solution bath with the slide was allowed to stay for a specific time interval.

Table 2. Numbers of slide and the time of deposition

Slides	Time of the solution bath
Slide 1	30min
Slide 2	2hr
Slide 3	5hr
Slide 4	10hr

Optical studies of Nickel sulphide (NiS₂) thin film

Optical study of nickel sulphide thin film was carried out in the wavelength range of 300-700 nm at room temperature. The spectral reflectance, absorbance and transmittance of the sample were obtained using Avantes single beam scanning UV-spectrophotometer.

Quality control and quality assurance was observed during the characterization, a blank substrate was used to run a quality check on the machine before running with thin film deposition on the substrate. Silicon wafer used as the normal for reflectance and air was used as the normal for transmittance. The basic principle of the machine is that it absorbs the source of UV incidents on

the sample and some are reflected while others are transmitted. Optical properties such as absorption coefficient, optical thickness, transmittance, reflectance and band gap energy and can be obtained by the following relation:

$$\alpha = \frac{\text{absorption}(A)}{\text{wavelength}} \tag{1}$$

$$t = \frac{\ln \frac{1}{T}}{\alpha} \tag{2}$$

where t is the optical thickness and α is the absorbance co-efficient

$$T = 10^{-A} \tag{3}$$

$$R = 10^{-(T+A)} \tag{4}$$

where T is transmittance and R is the reflectance [12]:

$$(\alpha h\nu) = A(h\nu - E_g)^n \tag{5}$$

where A is constant, n= 1/2 for direct allowed transition, E_g is optical band gap of the material, hν is the photon energy, h is the Planck constant

Results and Discussion

Completion times for single patient queues in the RPA system

The time distributions for the RPA system architecture implemented in the ManPy model for completing an individual.

Figure 2. Comparison of reflectance against wavelength for all slides at varying time.

Figure 3. Comparison of absorbance against wavelength for all slides at varying time.

Figure 4. Comparison of transmittance against wavelength for all slides at varying time.

Figure 5. Energy band gap of NiS thin film from this study.

Table 3. Phototherapy treatments and its useful UV range in comparison to NiS thin film mean optical properties for all exposure time from the study

S/N	Phototherapy treatment	UV range (nm)	Reflectance (%)	Absorbance (%)	Transmittance (T %)
1.	Skin cancer UVA	320 – 400 [13]	11.92	-8.22	72.91
2.	Skin cancer UVB	280 – 320 [14]	7.52	-37.89	17.84
3.	Skin conditions	280 – 400 [15,16]	11.07	-14.50	61.10
4.	hyperbilirubinemia	420 – 490 [17]	17.46	5.70	88.27

Reflectance

Comparing the reflectance of the film to the incident UV radiation for all slides with their varying time, fig. 2 shows a more reflectance on slide 2, having a maximum reflectance value of 26.12 at 580.24 nm. Slide 3 shows the least reflectance having a minimum value of 1.96 % at 300.47 nm. For all slides it is also observed that there was a gradual build up until reflectance was merely affected with an increase in wavelength.

Absorbance

Comparing the absorbance of the thin film to the incident UV radiation for all slides with varying time from fig 3, slide 1 has maximum absorbance of 90.34 % at 300.47 nm but falls sharply to about 6.12 % of which an increase in wavelength barely affects the absorbance. For slides 2 and 4 there was a gradual build up until absorbance was merely affected with an

increase in wavelength. For slide 3, there was no absorbance; the buildup was of no effect.

Transmittance

Comparing the transmittance of the film to the incident UV radiation for all slides at varying time, slide 4 having an exposure time of 10 hours transmits the UV radiation more compared to other slides with their exposure time as shown in fig. 4. It is observed that the transmittance increases with wavelength always to a point at 360.42 nm after which an increase in wavelength barely affects the amount of UV radiation transmitted from the thin film.

NiS optical properties and phototherapy UV range

From table 3, the phototherapy skin cancer UVA treatment range shows a mean value of 11.92 % reflectance, -8.22 % (build up) absorbance and 72.91 % transmittance. For skin cancer UVB treatment range, it shows a mean value of 7.52 % reflectance, -37.89 %

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